

COMPARISON OF ADJECTIVES IN PERSIAN-DARI AND PASHTO LANGUAGES

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Abstract: In the Pashto language, the adjective is different from the adjective in terms of number, gender, and mood due to its correspondence with the predicate, in modern Persian-Dari language. Unlike Pashto, adjectives in ancient and modern Persian are divided into two groups, the former and the latter. In the Persian language - a modern door between the adjective and some grammatical roles; As mentioned, there is no visible difference in terms of appearance, and the recognition of adjectives in this language is mostly based on grammatical features; If in Pashto language its structure in terms of number, gender and mood, all three have an important place.

Among the obvious topics in the Persian grammar books is the issue that the matching of adjectives and adverbs in the Persian language was taken from the Arabic language and there has never been such a rule in the Persian language; If the adjective in the ancient Iranian language and in the middle-western Iranian and Persian-Dari languages was always possible to match its object in terms of number, gender, and mood.

In this article, the authors decided to firstly express the opinions of some grammarians and the background of adjective and adjective matching in the Persian language, and then provide a general definition of the adjective in both Pashto and Persian-Dari languages, and compare the adjective Persian-Dari with Pashto language from different directions.

In this scientific article, a library research type and a scientific-comparative method have been used to validate the study of adjectives.

Key words: ancient Persian, grammar, Persian-Dari language, Pashto language, adjective.

Introduction

Persian-Dari and Pashto languages are among the co-rooted languages, which are considered to be from the family of Indo-Aryan languages, and the direct

influences of ancient languages such as Sanskrit and Avesta can be seen in these two co-rooted languages. It should be remembered that many characteristics of the ancient languages are also promoted and seen in today's Pashto language, and it should also be said that Persian-Dari and Pashto languages have many commonalities in different fields.

An adjective is a word that shows the state of something or a person, that is, an adjective makes the meaning of a noun more specific, obvious and limited (Yemin, 1397: 84). Adjective is a function that is mentioned in words for the following purposes, such as: (clarification, allocation, praise and pity...).

This research examines the structure of adjectives in cognate languages, and then the types of adjectives of the mentioned languages are compared with each other, and as a result of the analysis and analysis, the differences and similarities of the attributes of both languages are expressed.

Research background

The category of adjectives in Persian-Dari language is one of the topics that researchers have discussed a lot and they have dedicated researches to compare this topic in Persian-Dari language and other languages such as Arabic, Russian, German and English.

Despite the great importance of Pashto language for Dari languages, so far there has been no research on the comparison of adjectives in Persian-Dari and Pashto languages.

1. Adjective in Persian-Dari language

An adjective is a word that conveys the state and quality of something or someone, and its types are as follows: active adjective, passive adjective, superlative adjective, relative adjective (Qarib 1, 2013: 46). But the grammarians of Persian-Dari language have presented different opinions about the division of attributes, one of the most complete of these theories is the division of attributes in the Persian Grammar book by Abdul Rasool Khayampour. From Khayampour's point of view, there are five kinds of adjectives: absolute, reference, number, interrogative, ambiguity (P1,C6, P49).

The adjective is dependent on the noun and is not used independently; Because if it is used independently, it will no longer be an adjective or a dependent, but it will occupy the place of a noun and other things in a sentence (Wafa'i, 1390: 68). Also, the adjective in Parsi-Dari is singular when it is accompanied by a plural adjective, such as: "They didn't think that married men and women were married" (Majid 1:222). It is made from the absolute adjective with the suffix "-ter" (greater) and Samai, which itself consists of two groups of Samai, which are the remnants of the middle Persian adjectives (that, meh) and the adjectives. They are (P1,C1, P66).

Adjective in Persian-Dari language, unlike Pashto language, which considers it a type of noun, is placed in a separate category from words and is not classified as a noun. In the Persian-Dari language, adjectives do not match with adjectives in plural and singular; Whether it is singular or plural, such as:

By the grace of Saba, say that gazelle of Rana
that you have given us to the mountains of the desert.

(P1, C5, P4)

But whenever the adjective is removed and the adjective is placed in its place, that adjective is plural according to the meaning. As:

But what a bad name among the wise
We do not want the shame and name

(P1, C5, P8)

But the adjective in Pashto Hamra language is generally divided into two categories in terms of its dimensions.

A: Those attributes that do not have a perfect match with the described partner in terms of gender and number.

B: However, the feminine gender of the female gender shows complete correspondence in terms of number, such as:

Masculine singular	masculine plural	feminine singular	feminine plural
Blok pin	Blok pines	net net	net net
Good young man	good youth	good girl	good girl

(P1, C1, P203)

2. Adjective in Pashto language

There are no triple grades (to, better, best or big, bigger, biggest) to show adjectives in Pashto language like Persian-Dari language; Rather, it shows its rank and class by means of adat (dīr and khora), such as: (good, very good, very very good or white, very white, very very white) (P1, C7, P202).

Adjectives in Pashto language are divided into several types, which are as follows: main adjective, relative adjective, indicative adjective, numerical adjective, interrogative adjective, present adjective and passive adjective. (P1, C11, P39).

In the Pashto language, the cognate adjective is used in terms of (gender, number and mood). But the adjective in Pashto Hamra language is generally divided into two categories in terms of its dimensions.

A: Those attributes that do not have a perfect match with the described partner in terms of gender and number.

B: However, the feminine gender of the described companion shows complete correspondence in terms of number (P1, C7, P203).

In the grammars of Pashto language, it has been mentioned that common adjectives do not match completely in terms of gender and number; But this statement is worthy of consideration. Those common adjectives that end with the vowel letter (a) show agreement in terms of feminine singular and plural. The multiplicity of dialects in Pashto has caused problems on the one hand, but on the other hand, it has contributed to the structural completion of this well-rounded language. For example, in the Kandahari dialect and in the neighboring regions, nouns that end with the vowel letter (a), such as (sadeh, pajah, fayal) show complete agreement with the feminine plural.

Masculine singular masculine plural feminine singular feminine plural

Simple girl simple girl simple girl

On foot boy, On foot boys, On foot girl, On foot girls.

beautiful girl, beautiful girls, beautiful boy, beautiful boys.

جمع مؤنث	مفرد مؤنث	جمع مذکر	مفرد مذکر
سادې نجونې	ساده نجلۍ	ساده هلکان	ساده هلک
پيادې نجونې	پياده نجلۍ	پياده هلکان	پياده هلک
بنايستي نجونې	بنايسته نجلۍ	بنايسته هلکان	بنايسته هلک

It should be mentioned that in Pashto, the adjective usually comes before the adjective, such as Sur Kamis, Levi Shahir, and Duque Young.

3. Analysis and matching

In Persian-Dari language, there is a strong connection between adjective and adjective in terms of meaning, but in Pashto language, this connection is obvious both in terms of meaning and in terms of structure. Adjective recognition scales in Persian-Dari language are syntactic, but in Pashto, both structural indicators and syntactic indicators are involved. In the Persian-Dari language, the adjective comes after the adjective, such as (a good boy and a white book); But in Pashto language, unlike Persian-Dari language, the adjective comes first and then the adjective, like: white book, good boy.

3. 1. Absolute Adjective

It is to express the state of something or someone absolutely and completely without comparing it or showing its degree and size. For example, good, bad, white, lazy, strong, intelligent... In normal cases, this kind of adjective is placed after the adjective, and the adjective is connected with the adjective with the sign of increase /i/, such as: the powerful hand, A good person... and whenever the adjective ends with the vowel /, o, a, á, ú/, in this case it is a sign of the increase of /yi/, which comes in the form of /-y/, for example : Good weather, faithful acquaintance and Indian lemon... (P1, C11, P85).

According to this adjective, in Pashto language, they say adjectives that express the states and characteristics that belong to the essence of a noun, good or bad, such as:

Mashr al-Makhli, good al-Makhli, in which his mashr is good is one of the main or absolute attributes.

It should be remembered that there are two types of absolute adjectives in Pashto language: A- Simple: the one that has a component, i.e., it is a single word, such as: (Good and bad) This type of adjective is completely dependent on sama. B- Compound: It is composed of two or more components, such as: Toriyali, Napoh, Khatgar Rekhteen (P1, C9, P108).

3. 2. relative adjective

It is a relative adjective that refers to something or a place (P1, C4, P55).

In Persian-Dari language, relative adjective has the following suffixes:

A - /y/: in words ending with a consonant, for example: Balkhi, Herati, Sangi, Khobi, Khashti...

B / E / For example: one year old, three months old, ten days old, green...

C. /Yen/ For example: Zarin, Simin, Crystal, Ghamin...

d- /ineh/ for example: simine, pashmina...

For example: childish, feminine, masculine, romantic...

And - / single / for example: double, five, single...

The equivalent of this adjective in Pashto language is to attribute someone or something to a place or something. A place or something that is related to a noun is attributed to it and that noun is said to be attributed. Some famous signs of relative adjectives are (val, melina, khil, zi, yaz, yen, ni...) such as: Kameh-Wal, Kabuli, Sulaiman-Khel, Sedozi, Oseni, Vareshmin, Charehiz, etc... (P1, C9, P108).

3. 3. Subjective adjective

It is an adjective that shows that it describes a work or has a state (Emad Afshar, 1372: 62).

In Persian-Dari language, it has the following suffixes:

A- / don't/ which comes at the end of the imperative verb, such as: asking, knitting, wanting...

صفت فاعلی	مصدر
گرځند	گرځېدل
سوځند	سوځېدل
ژرند	ژرېدل

B- / that/ such as: desiring, running, running, asking...

صفت فاعلی	مصدر
خوځندی	خوځېدل
رپندی	رپېدل

کرپندی	کرپیدل
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C- / A/ which also comes at the end of the imperative verb, such as: Shakiba, Khana, Joya...

صفت فاعلی	مصدر
پوونده	پوول
څرنده	څریدل
چلنده	چلېدل

D- /r/ is often at the end of the past participle such as: buyer, demander, arrester...

صفت فاعلی	مصدر
پوهاند	پوهیدل
ژراند	ژرېدل
بهاند	بهېدل

E- /gar/ which mostly comes at the end of the past tense and past participle, such as: learner, pious, provardgar...

صفت فاعلی	مصدر
ساتندوی	ساتل
گټندوی	گټل
پېژندوی	پېژندل

And /work/ which is often added to the end of the meaning noun, such as: oppressor, forgetful...

Z - /gar/ also at the end of the noun meaning such as: Dadgar, Ramshgar, Bidadgar... (P1, C4, Ps47-48).

The equivalent of the active adjective in the neighboring Persian-Dari language, that is, Pashto, is the active adjective, which, in addition to showing the meaning and concept of the noun, also occurs, such as: Vohunki, Telonki, Chalonki, Ugumani, etc. (P1, C12, P91).

Active adjectives in Pashto language have suffixes like Persian-Dari language, but in Pashto these suffixes are placed instead of infinitive signs and form active adjectives, such as:

A - /Nd/ This suffix is often placed in place of the infinitive (ydel) and indicates the meaning of active adjective, for example: Active adjective infinitive.

3. 4. Objective adjective

It is to know the object. In Persian-Dari language, the passive adjective is formed from the past participle root with the suffix /-e/, as: broken, eaten, taken, killed...

The passive adjective is also placed after the noun it belongs to, which has an increasing sign, such as: broken heart, animal killed, spoken... (P1, C13, P88).

Passive adjectives are sometimes reduced like active adjectives. in such a way that the second part of it becomes a verb:

O army of your refuge, in the door of his people from your door. (P1, C4, P53)

The other three were in Yazdan, ungrateful, hiding his body unknown (P1, C3, Ps10-70)

The passive adjective in Pashto language is made with the suffixes (e, y, and wanki), such as: (wawaheh, vasateh, sati, leki, prê-kedonki, vehl kedonki, etc.) (P1, C10, P41).

Adjectives correspond with adjectives in terms of their states, and the changes that occur in adjectives in terms of gender are also reflected in adjectives. As:

3. 5. superlative adjective

It is that the word "Ter" is added at the end and its meaning is the preference of the adjective over another person who is a partner and equal to him in the existence of the adjective, and it should be attached only to the end of the adjective and the words that have the meaning of the adjective. Like: more eloquent, superior...

The superlative adjective is used in three ways:

A- With "of" such as: wisdom is more useful than wealth - a little planning is more useful than a large army.

B- With "that" like: knowledge is better than wealth - character is more attractive than face.

C- With "Yen" such as: the least, the most virtuous, the greatest (P1, C4, Ps55-54).

There are no triple degrees (to, better, best or big, bigger, biggest) to show a superlative adjective in Pashto language like Persian-Dari language; Rather, it shows its rank and class by means of adat (a lot and a lot), such as: (Good, very good, very very good, whit, very whit, very very whit) (P1, C7, P202).

It should be remembered that one of the grammatical characteristics of the adjective in the Persian-Dari language is that it never accepts the plural suffix and whenever such words accept the plural sign, they are included in the noun group, for example: Nikan, know... There is no such feature in the Pashto adjective. Also, the superior comparative adjective in Persian-Dari language is mostly used as an adverb, which means that it is related to the verb. For example: Parveen is more beautiful than Gulalai. There is such a rule in the Pashto language as well, such as: Parveen is beautiful than Gulalai. ((Parveen ter Gulalai Dera Khkuly dy)).

Result

By examining and matching adjectives in the important sources of Persian-Dari and Pashto languages, the following results can be enumerated:

The adjective is dependent on the noun and is not used independently; Because if it is used independently, it will no longer be an adjective or a dependent, but it will

occupy the place of a noun or something else in the sentence. Also, in Persian-Dari, the adjective is singular when the adjective is plural.

Adjective in Persian-Dari language, unlike Pashto language, which considers it a type of noun, is placed in a separate category from words and is not classified as a noun. In the Persian-Dari language, adjectives do not match with adjectives in plural and singular; Whether the noun is singular or plural, whenever the adjective is removed and an adjective is placed in its place, that adjective becomes plural according to the meaning.

In the Pashto language, adjectives are classified according to (gender, number and mood), but adjectives in Pashto are generally divided into two categories in terms of their dimensions.

A: Those attributes that do not have a perfect match with the described partner in terms of gender and number.

B: But the described feminine gender shows complete correspondence in terms of number.

To show adjectives in Pashto language, like Persian-Dari language, there are no triple degrees (to, better, best or big, bigger, biggest); Rather, it shows its level and class by the habits (Dere and Khora), such as: (Good, Good, Good, Khora Good)

In Persian-Dari language, there is a strong connection between adjective and adjective in terms of meaning, but in Pashto language, this connection is obvious both in terms of meaning and in terms of structure. Adjective recognition scales in Persian-Dari language are syntactic, but in Pashto, both structural indicators and syntactic indicators are involved. In the Persian-Dari language, the adjective comes after the adjective, such as (a good boy); But in Pashto language, unlike Persian-Dari language, adjectives come first and then adjectives, such as: (GOOD BOY)

It should be remembered that one of the grammatical characteristics of the adjective in the Persian-Dari language is that it never accepts the plural suffix, and whenever such words accept the plural sign, they are included in the noun group, for example: Nikan, know... that such There is no special feature in Pashto language. Also, the superior comparative adjective in Persian-Dari language mostly comes as an adverb, which means that it is related to the verb. For example: Parveen is more beautiful than Gulali. There is such a rule in the Pashto language as well, such as: Parveen Ter Gulalai Dera Kayesta Dah.

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